

Entrepreneurship and Regional Development

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 2

Month: February

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2320-4168

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Dharani, R.

“Entrepreneurship and Regional Development.” *Shanlax International Journal of Commerce*, vol. 7, no. S2, 2019, pp. 64–68.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2563779>

R.Dharani, (B.Com[CA]),

II – M.Com[CA], Annai Women's College, Karur

Abstract

Entrepreneurship and Regional development is considered as one of the key factors for the nation's development and progress. It is a globally oriented activity which makes us creative with innovation of new ideas or renovations of business ideas available already or in practice. The growth of entrepreneurship improves the standard of living of people in the various regions of the country. Entrepreneurship and Regional development are two terms which distinct in its nature but when connected gives the meaning that the development of the region can be made with entrepreneurship as it creates employment and increases the per capita income through which the development of the nation is measured. The entrepreneurs face many problems and there are various obstacles and challenges to achieve their goals. Government should also take responsible to bring the awareness about the entrepreneurship among the youth, women, and unemployed persons irrespective of their age. The government should be ready to introduce new beneficiary schemes for them. The government should put all its efforts to take various initiatives to develop entrepreneurship in all regions of the country.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Economic development, Challenges, Government initiative.

Introduction

This paper indicates how entrepreneurship is important to the regional development of a nation like India. Entrepreneurship is the term which is being very popular among the people in the past decades. An Entrepreneur is a leader who puts his effort for the nurturing economic growth and development. The person is regarded as an ‘Entrepreneur’ who get into entrepreneurship. Simply entrepreneurship is the activity of running own business and get income from it. These entrepreneurs don't search for jobs, hence they play major role in reducing the consequences of structural unemployment through self-employment. Entrepreneurship stimulates social and economic development in the national, regional and even in the local level of the economy. Entrepreneurs carry out managerial activities in running one's own business. It is linked with entrepreneurial activities and creativity and their ability to run their business and generate new business idea which support to development of innovation which is considered as one of the pillars of economic development and competitive regions. Thus the effective entrepreneurship with the quantitative and qualitative feature helps to achieve the goal of economic development. Still the development

of the entire nation depends upon the region which is a fundamental basis of economic and social life. For understanding the fundamentals of economic growth and development Entrepreneurship, regional development and culture as well as other phenomena such as technology transfer or women's entrepreneurship.

Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship is the process of designing, launching and running a new business, which is often initially a small business later which may turn into a big business or even a big organization. The people who carry out these business are called as entrepreneurs. Risks are being carried out by them in various ways to make or earn profit. Entrepreneurship comprises of three dimensions working together such as ingenious government programmes, framework conditions and innovative ideas. It also includes the psychological, economic and sociological academic fields in the process of entrepreneurship. It also includes the organisational activities such as planning, organizing, etc. Entrepreneurship plays the role of the following,

- Innovator
- Planner
- Communicator
- Risk bearer
- Decision maker
- Continuous learner
- Belief in themselves

There are various factors which motivates the entrepreneurship such as to achieve the goals, opportunities available to them, a special values and norms possessed by themselves.

Regional Development

Development is the process of growth movement from one position to another in the positive way or in the upward position. The nation is divided into various states and these states are divided into districts. These divisions are made to make the managerial functions easier. In the similar way the regions are the divided part of a nation. Development is simply a change, a change into better. For example, a child develops into a adult, and a plant develops into a tree like wise the region develops in a better way. These developments are measured in the way of the income level, quality of life, etc. Regional development is not only based on the geographical one but with the development of human beings. These developments include the economic condition, happiness and the quality of people living. Though they are considered, the important aspect of development is that the increase in the income level of the people in the region which supports to the regional development by increasing the per capital income. The nation has various regions in it, but development is not equally done. One region grows better than the other region because of the various factors. The term balanced regional development does not mean that they are equally developed; it means that they are developed to the fullest of the resources available in the region.

Entrepreneurship and Regional Development

The entrepreneurship and regional development are interdependent one for the growth of the region. It is a activity for the creation and to bring development in a region economically and socially. Rather than entrepreneurship to make betterment in the region, local authorities should play a major role with entrepreneurial behaviors on one hand and to increase the benefit of the regions on the other. Development among the regions differs because of the resources available in it. Therefore the resources of the regions should be increased or should be protected against exploitation. This

may enable the external investors to do business in their region which automatically develops the region. This may vary depending upon the country. Another important factor is that people of the region works together to encourage regional development. This entrepreneurship creates employment opportunities for the others of the same region which makes everyone employed in a particular region. If it is carried out in the entire nation then the problem of unemployment does not prevails.

Literature Review

The following are reviews given by the various authors for the better understanding of the concept,

Entrepreneurship is not confined to any one particular industry, country or group of persons; it exists in everybody but depends on individuals desire. Enterprising behavior has been found in all societies, and in all types of economic circumstances. Whilst the term usually refers just to an individual, it is also possible to find whole organization than can be classified as entrepreneurial in the way they do business and seek to grow **(Michael Schaper)**

The Entrepreneurship is an activity dedicated to initiation, maintenance and development of a profit oriented business **(cole)**

The entrepreneurship is an innovation act who presupposes the endowment of the existing resources with the capacity of producing wealth **(Drucker)**

The entrepreneurship is the creation of new organizations.**(Gartner)**

The entrepreneurship is the process of creating something different, with value, by allotting the necessary time and effort, pre supposing the taking of financial, social and physical risks, and obtaining monetary rewards and personal satisfaction. **(Hisrich and Peters)**

Challenges Faced by Entrepreneurs

The entrepreneur before becoming successful in his business faces many problems and challenges in the society when he was a new entrepreneur. The challenges are,

- Family challenges
- Social challenges
- Technological challenges
- Financial challenges
- Policy challenges

To contribute to the development of the region where he lives, the entrepreneurs should come up with the above mentioned challenges. The entrepreneurs should convince his family about the idea he has for his business and also be financially satisfied because the idea alone cannot give a fruitful business.

Role of Entrepreneurship in Regional Development

Entrepreneurship plays a important role in improving the standard of living of the country. As a startup founder we work hard to develop our business to make profit out of it for our sake. But actually we are doing for our local community, state, region and finally the country as a whole. The following roles are played by the entrepreneurs in the economic development of the nation.

• Creation of Wealth and Distributes

The wealth are created by the entrepreneurs and equally distributed among the various regions in the society of the country.

• Job Creation

The skills are used by the entrepreneurs efficiently and promote employment opportunities even to other individuals.

- **Increase in GDP and Per Capital Income**

Entrepreneurship increases the GDP of the country and thus help in the development of the nation.

- **Improve Standard of Living**

As entrepreneurship creates employment opportunities it automatically improves the standard of living.

- **Increase exports**

As everyone individually do the business, the number of business increases and hence the exports increases.

- **Development in community**

The development of entrepreneurs in the region helps to develop the community. The development is the main goal of it.

- **Large scale employment**

The entrepreneurship creates large employment to unemployed persons, women and irrespective of their age any one can start entrepreneurship.

- **Reduces concentration of economic power**

Basically economic power is concentrated within the hands of few individuals doing business but the entrepreneurship reduces this concentration of economic power as it distributes among everyone.

- **Creating innovation**

As the entrepreneurs major asset is their ideas into practice. This innovation is their main resources and new combination, strategies and policies are used.

- **Promotes overall development**

The entrepreneurship at the initial stage during development create demand for the other type of units and thus develop the area, facilitates overall development.

- **Creation of new business**

The business created from the introduction of new ideas and strategies and provides employment aspect to the individuals.

- **Personal growth**

Without waiting for the jobs provided the youth themselves create jobs and grown on the two aspects of personal development such as skills, increase ability and the other is the development of the surroundings.

- **Enables social change**

Social change is possible only with the change in the people of the region. The change should be in the positive way of improving the nation.

Entrepreneurship in India

The entrepreneurship has different point of view that it is mainly for the youths and those who are educated or who are well financially settled or those who have better idea or those who are hard worker or only for men. This different point of view on the entrepreneurship prevails in India before the decades. But now the people are well cleared about the activities of entrepreneurship and even courses are being offered. The entrepreneurship provides employment opportunities to everyone irrespective of age, gender, educational qualification and even financially not settled person can be a entrepreneur as there are many offers of loan facilities available to them. The first entrepreneurs in India are since from kingdom. Later a particular community alone has done that work .But now

India generates entrepreneurs from all communities. The various changes prevail in the system of entrepreneurship as now. As technology gets developed the growth of entrepreneurship also shows improvement. The qualities of entrepreneurship get changed beyond time and new qualities and skills are required. Therefore entrepreneurship is in the growing trend in India.

Conclusion

The Entrepreneurship is not only simply starting the business but also the entrepreneur should possess the creativity and should be intelligent about his work. The entrepreneurs should have an attitude of positive view during the failure. He should have guts to face the problems and challenges in achieving the goals. The entrepreneurship should enable for the development, it means they should contribute for the development of a nation. The entrepreneurs should possess a key skill and abilities for being successful. He should be well prepared for the purpose of facing the opportunities and external environmental condition. The government should play an important role in making the regions of a country with balanced regional development. The regions are to be protected with the available resources and the policies are to be framed to increase the resources further. The opportunities are to be well used by the entrepreneurs of various regions. Entrepreneurships create a competitive environment for the new entrepreneurs entering the market. Thus entrepreneurship contributes a major role in the economic development and increase in per capita income of a country.

References

- Misra, S., & Kumar, S. "Resourcefulness: A Proximal Conceptualization of Entrepreneurial Behaviour", J. Entrep.,
- Drucker, P., "Innovation and Entrepreneurship: Practice and Principle", Harper Business, New York.
- Swetha, T., & Rao, KV. "Entrepreneurship in India". International Journal of Social Science and Interdisciplinary Research. 2013.
- Santhi, N., & Kumar, SR., "Entrepreneurship Challenges and Opportunities in India". 2011. www.google.com